

SOUND COMPARISONS

MASTER REFERENCE DOI TO LINK ALL INDIVIDUAL COMPONENTS OF THE *SOUND COMPARISONS* PROJECT

Paul Heggarty

This Zenodo upload – <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595670> – serves only as a master reference for all website/database publications that are components of the overall *Sound Comparisons* project.

The overall project homepage at <https://soundcomparisons.com> hosts a series of ‘studies’, each covering a different language family and/or regions, and each with its own different combination of authors, hence the need also to publish them all individually and independently.

As of this first Zenodo upload in December 2019, the twelve components on the *Sound Comparisons* website are:

- Europe <https://soundcomparisons.com/Europe>
- Germanic <https://soundcomparisons.com/Germanic>
- Englishes <https://soundcomparisons.com/Englishes>
- Romance <https://soundcomparisons.com/Romance>
- Celtic <https://soundcomparisons.com/Celtic>
- Slavic and Baltic <https://soundcomparisons.com/Slavic>
- Andes <https://soundcomparisons.com/Andes>
- Mapudungun <https://soundcomparisons.com/Mapudungun>
- Brazil <https://soundcomparisons.com/Brazil>
- Vanuatu <https://soundcomparisons.com/Vanuatu>
- West Papua <https://soundcomparisons.com/WestPapua>
- Mixe <https://soundcomparisons.com/Mixe>

These twelve components are all already (December 2019) available on the <https://soundcomparisons.com> website. Progressively from December 2019 onwards, they will be released individually also as website/database publications on Zenodo, each with its own DOI, although all cross-referenced to this master reference DOI for the *Sound Comparisons* project as a whole.